

Communication between DNA Superconductors through non-observable fields in a generalized brane theory

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Recently, using the concepts in string theory, a model for considering the superconductivity in graphene wormhole has been proposed. In this paper, using similarity between topology of this system with DNA and generalizing M-theory, a new model and algebra for describing the superconductivity of a DNA within the nucleus is suggested. In this model, DNAs live on the connected region of two $4N-2$ dimensional branes with N -dimensional algebra. Each of these branes have itself gauge fields and by each compacting, some scalar strings decay into fermions. Also, if compactings aren't complete, some fermions are lost and other fermions become free. In connected region, a brane and its fields could be observed and other brane and its fields couldn't be observed, however, their signatures could be considered. In this system, in additions to non-symmetric gauge fields like photons and gravitons, there are some full symmetric fields which couldn't be observed and move along one of branes. These fields connect DNAs and produce some currents between them. However, in connected region, total current of a DNA is zero and external current which enters from one side, immediately goes out from other end. Also, magnetic fields which are induced from one side, itself or another type of fields with the same energy is repelled from other side and total fields of a DNA could be zero. Thus, a DNA could act like a superconductor which communicate with other DNAs through non-observable fields. Also, topology of total N -dimensional branes including DNAs and fields could be shrink to one.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Around 40 years ago, some scientists have proposed a dynamical model to describe DNA as superconductor. In their model, superconductivity is emerged by a radiation-induced harmonic oscillation of a parcel of π electrons between the reference level and critical temperatures [1]. In parallel, in that time, another group have used of Little's formalism to investigate the possibility of superconductive regions at room temperature in organic polymers. They have calculated the Coulomb and effective attractive terms for the polycytosine homopolynucleotide. They have concluded that one cannot exclude the possibility of superconductive-type enhanced conductivity in some regions of DNA [2]. In 2001, some other investigators have measured the conductivity in double-stranded DNA molecules and shown that the resistance per molecule is less than 100 kilohm and varies weakly with temperature. Their results have implied that DNA molecules can be conducting down to millikelvin temperature and that phase coherence is maintained over several hundred nanometers [3]. These considerations may be connected with parallel investigation in DNA transductions and waves. In 2011, Montagnier and his group [4, 5] have shown that viral DNAs could emit some frequencies of waves. Also, they have shown that electromagnetic waves could help viral RNAs transportation from a vessel to another one. In their model, vessels could be replaced by cells and water could be replaced by liquids within cells. Also, electromagnetic waves could be radiated by π electrons in DNA superconductor.

On the other hand, a DNA has been built from hexagonal and pentagonal molecules. This system is very similar to a graphene wormhole [6, 7] (See figure 1). A graphene sheet is also formed from hexagonal molecules. Up to date, many scientists have tried to induce some defects in graphene sheets and produce graphene superconductor. For example, they have shown that a tubular structure could increase conductivity. This structure is very close to a DNA inductor. Thus, by using similarity between two systems, one can design a model to describe the conductivity in a DNA. Previously, using the concepts in string theory and M-theory, a mechanism for calculating the current density of hexagonal and pentagonal molecules in a graphene superconductor has been proposed [8]. Generalizing this consideration to hexagonal/pentagonal molecules of a DNA, we can discover the mystery of superconductivity of DNAs within the nucleus.

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The outline of this paper is as follows: In section II, generalizing concepts in string theory and M-theory, we suggest a new algebra which could be applied for topology of DNAs. In section III, we calculate the current density and assert that a DNA is a superconductor.

II. AN ALGEBRA FOR A DNA

FIG. 1: Topology of a DNA could be similar to topology of a graphene wormhole

Previously, using the concepts in M-theory, a new algebra has been introduced to describe evolutions of current densities within the graphene wormholes [8] (See figure 1). The topology of graphene wormholes are very close to the topology of DNAs. Both graphene sheet and DNAs are formed from hexagonal and pentagonal molecules. Although, atoms within a graphene wormhole are more carbons and atoms within the DNA could be carbon, Nitrogen, Oxygen, Phosphor and others. Using similarities between two systems, we generalize the algebra applied in a graphene system to describe the conductivity of a DNA.

Newly, it has been approved that all Dp -branes in string theories are formed from $D0$ -branes which obey from Lie-two-algebras with two dimensional brackets [8–18]. Also, all Mp -branes in M -theory are built from $M0$ -branes which obey from a Lie-three-algebra with three dimensional brackets [19–22]. Then, by applying the Lie- N -algebra and extending dimensions to M , we built a new theory which includes all the properties of string theory and M -theory and resolve the puzzles in them. To observe this, we use of the action for the Dp -brane [15–18]:

$$S = -\frac{T_{Dp}}{2} \int d^{p+1}x \sum_{n=1}^p \beta_n \chi_{[\mu_0}^{\mu_0} \chi^{\mu_1} \dots \chi^{\mu_n]} \quad (1)$$

where

$$\chi_\nu^\mu \equiv \delta_\nu^\mu \text{STr} \left(-\det(P_{ab}[E_{mn}E_{mi}(Q^{-1} + \delta)^{ij}E_{jn}] + \lambda F_{ab}) \det(Q_j^i) \right)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

and

$$E_{mn} = G_{mn} + B_{mn}, \quad Q_j^i = \delta_j^i + i\lambda[X^j, X^k]E_{kj} \quad (3)$$

$\lambda = 2\pi l_s^2$ and $G_{ab} = \eta_{ab} + \partial_a X^i \partial_b X^i$ and X^i are scalar strings that couple to branes. In this equation, $a, b = 0, 1, \dots, p$ are the world-volume indices of the Dp -branes, $i, j, k = p+1, \dots, 9$ are the indices of the transverse space, and m, n are related to ten-dimensional spacetime indices. Also, $T_{Dp} = \frac{1}{g_s (2\pi)^p l_s^{p+1}}$ denotes the tension of the Dp -brane, l_s is the string length and g_s denotes the string coupling. Now, we can assert that the action of the Dp -brane can be built by summing over actions of $D0$ -branes. To this end, we apply the rules below [9, 11, 15–18]:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_{a=0}^p \Sigma_{m=0}^9 &\rightarrow \frac{1}{(2\pi l_s)^p} \int d^{p+1}x \sigma \Sigma_{m=p+1}^9 \Sigma_{a=0}^p & \lambda &= 2\pi l_s^2 \\ i, j &= p+1, \dots, 9 & a, b &= 0, 1, \dots, p & m, n &= 0, 1, \dots, 9 \\ i, j &\rightarrow a, b \Rightarrow [X^a, X^i] &= i\lambda \partial_a X^i & [X^a, X^b] &= \frac{i\lambda F^{ab}}{2} \\ \frac{1}{Q} &\rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^p \frac{1}{Q} (\partial_a X^i \partial_b X^i + \frac{\lambda^2}{4} (F^{ab})^2)^n \\ \det(Q_j^i) &\rightarrow \det(Q_j^i) \prod_{n=1}^p \det(\partial_{a_n} X^i \partial_{b_n} X^i + \frac{\lambda^2}{4} (F^{a_n b_n})^2) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

FIG. 2: Branes and their fields.

Above rules show that when two ends of a string is confined to a brane, it forms a gauge field like photon. If one end of it be free or coupled to other brane, it makes a scalar field. If two ends of a string connect to each other and

brane, it makes a symmetric field like graviton (See figure 2). Applying the above laws, we can show that the action of Dp-branes can be given in terms of two dimensional brackets [9, 11, 15–18]:

$$S_{Dp} = -(T_{D0})^p \int dt \sum_{n=1}^p \beta_n \left(\delta_{b_1 b_2 \dots b_n}^{a_1 a_2 \dots a_n} L_{a_1}^{b_1} \dots L_{a_n}^{b_n} \right)^{1/2}$$

$$(L)_a^b = Tr \left(\sum_{a,b=0}^p \Sigma_{j=p+1}^9 ([X^a, X^j][X_b, X_j] + [X^a, X^b][X_b, X_a] + [X^i, X^j][X_i, X_j]) \right) \quad (5)$$

where we have used of the antisymmetric properties for δ . At this stage, we can show that the above action is built by summing over the actions of D0-branes by using the definition below for the D0-brane [8–18]:

$$S_{D0,anti-sym} = -T_{D0} \int dt Tr(\Sigma_{m=0}^9 [X^m, X^n]^2) \quad (6)$$

Above action includes anti-symmetrical brackets. We should regard below symmetric brackets so.

$$S_{D0,sym} = -T_{D0} \int dt Tr(\Sigma_{m=0}^9 \{X^m, X^n\}^2) \quad (7)$$

Summing over symmetrical and anti-symmetrical brackets gives:

$$S_{D0,tot} = -T_{D0} \int dt Tr(\Sigma_{m=0}^9 ([X^m, X^n]^2 + \{X^m, X^n\}^2)) \quad (8)$$

However, above notation is wrong and we should write actions by below terms:

$$S_{D0,tot} = -T_{D0} \int dt Tr(\Sigma_{m=0}^9 (\langle [X^m, X^n] | [X^m, X^n] \rangle + \langle \{X^m, X^n\} | \{X^m, X^n\} \rangle)) \quad (9)$$

Above action is complete and includes multiplying bra and kets of symmetric and anti-symmetric communications. Above brackets obey of below rules:

$$\{X^m, X^n\} = \epsilon^{ij} \frac{\partial X^m}{\partial y^i} \frac{\partial X^n}{\partial y^j} \quad (10)$$

$$\langle [X^m, X^n] | [X^m, X^n] \rangle = h^{ab} \epsilon^{ai} \epsilon^{bj} \frac{\partial X^m}{\partial y^a} \frac{\partial X^n}{\partial y^i} \frac{\partial X^m}{\partial y^j} \frac{\partial X^n}{\partial y^b} \quad (11)$$

$$\{X^m, X^n\} = \eta^{ij} \frac{\partial X^m}{\partial y^i} \frac{\partial X^n}{\partial y^j} \quad (12)$$

$$\langle \{X^m, X^n\} | \{X^m, X^n\} \rangle = h^{ab} \eta^{ai} \eta^{bj} \frac{\partial X^m}{\partial y^a} \frac{\partial X^n}{\partial y^i} \frac{\partial X^m}{\partial y^j} \frac{\partial X^n}{\partial y^b} \quad (13)$$

By using above rules, we can rewrite the action of D0-brane as below:

$$S_{D0,tot} = -T_{D0} \int dt Tr(\Sigma_{m=0}^9 ((-1) \frac{\partial X^m}{\partial y^a} \frac{\partial X^n}{\partial y^i} \frac{\partial X^m}{\partial y^j} \frac{\partial X^n}{\partial y^b})) \quad (14)$$

We can rewrite -1 as multiplying of two i:

$$-X^m X^n = [(i)X^m][(i)X^n] \quad (15)$$

Substituting above equation in equation (14) gives:

$$S_{D0,tot} = -T_{D0} \int dt Tr(\Sigma_{m=0}^9 \left(\frac{\partial X^m}{\partial y^a} \frac{\partial X^n}{\partial y^i} \frac{\partial [(i)X^m]}{\partial y^j} \frac{\partial [(i)X^n]}{\partial y^b} \right)) \quad (16)$$

Also, we replace summation with integrals [8–16]:

$$\Sigma_{m=0}^9 \Rightarrow \int dy^a dy^i dy^j dy^b \Sigma_{m=4}^9 \quad (17)$$

Now, we can rewrite the action of D0-brane as below:

$$S_{D0,tot} = -T_{D0} \int dt Tr(\Sigma_{m=4}^9 \int dy^a dy^i dy^j dy^b \left(\frac{\partial X^m}{\partial y^a} \frac{\partial X^n}{\partial y^i} \frac{\partial [(i)X^m]}{\partial y^j} \frac{\partial [(i)X^n]}{\partial y^b} \right)) \quad (18)$$

We can multiply the above action by four exponential in below form:

$$1 = e^{-\pi X^m \cdot X_m} e^{-\pi X^n \cdot X_n} e^{-\pi [(i)X^m] \cdot [(i)X_m]} e^{-\pi [(i)X^m] \cdot (i)X_m} \quad (19)$$

Consequently, the action becomes:

$$S_{D0,tot} = -T_{D0} \int dt Tr(\Sigma_{m=4}^9 \int dy^a dy^i dy^j dy^b \left(\frac{\partial X^m}{\partial y^a} \frac{\partial X^n}{\partial y^i} \frac{\partial [(i)X^m]}{\partial y^j} \frac{\partial [(i)X^n]}{\partial y^b} \right) \times e^{-\pi X^m \cdot X_m} e^{-\pi X^n \cdot X_n} e^{-\pi [(i)X^m] \cdot [(i)X_m]} e^{-\pi [(i)X^m] \cdot (i)X_m}) \quad (20)$$

by using definitions of delta functions in below forms

$$\delta(X^m) = \zeta \int dy^a \frac{\partial X^m}{\partial y^a} e^{-\pi X^m \cdot X_m} \quad (21)$$

we can assert that the action of D0-brane could shrink to one:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_{m=4}^9 &\Rightarrow \int d^6 X \\ S_{D0,tot} &= -T_{D0} \zeta^4 \int dt \int d^2 X \left(\int d^4 X \delta^4(X) \right) = \\ &= -T_{D0} \zeta^4 \int dt \int d^2 X = T_{D0} \zeta^4 V^3 \Rightarrow -1 \\ E_{D0,tot} &= -S_{D0,tot} \Rightarrow 1 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

This is an interesting result that comes from calculations. All branes are built from D0-branes and now these branes shrink to point and their energies shrink to one (See figure 3). Thus, total energy of universe is a constant. We can generalize this discussion to 4N-2 dimensional space-time and N-dimensional algebra:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{E0,tot} &= \\ &= -T_{E0} \int dt Tr(\Sigma_{n_1 \dots n_n=0}^{4N-2} (\langle [X^{n_1}, \dots, X^{n_N}] | [X^{n_1}, \dots, X^{n_N}] \rangle + \langle \{X^{n_1}, \dots, X^{n_N}\} | \{X^{n_1}, \dots, X^{n_N}\} \rangle)) \\ S_{E0,tot} &\Rightarrow \int d^N X \delta^N(X) \Rightarrow -1 \\ E_{E0,tot} &= -S_{E0,tot} \Rightarrow 1 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where

FIG. 3: Topology of a D0/E0-brane could be shrink to a point with energy of one.

$$\begin{aligned}
[T^{\alpha_{n_1}}, T^{\alpha_{n_2}} \dots T^{\alpha_{n_N}}] &= f_{\alpha_L}^{\alpha_{n_1} \dots \alpha_{n_N}} T^L \\
\{\bar{T}^{\alpha_{n_1}}, \bar{T}^{\alpha_{n_2}} \dots \bar{T}^{\alpha_{n_N}}\} &= \eta_{\alpha_L}^{\alpha_{n_1} \dots \alpha_{n_N}} \bar{T}^L \\
\langle T^\alpha, T^\beta \rangle &= h^{\alpha\beta} \\
\langle \bar{T}^\alpha, \bar{T}^\beta \rangle &= \delta^{\alpha\beta} \\
[X^{L_1}, X^{L_2}, \dots, X^{L_N}] &= [X_{\alpha_1}^{L_1} T^{\alpha_1}, X_{\alpha_2}^{L_2} T^{\alpha_2}, \dots, X_{\alpha_N}^{L_N} T^{\alpha_N}] \\
\{X^{L_1}, X^{L_2}, \dots, X^{L_N}\} &= \{X_{\alpha_1}^{L_1} \bar{T}^{\alpha_1}, X_{\alpha_2}^{L_2} \bar{T}^{\alpha_2}, \dots, X_{\alpha_N}^{L_N} \bar{T}^{\alpha_N}\}
\end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

Above generalized action could be compacted $2N-4$ times, remove some strings from its branes and reproduce the action of D0-brane by substituting ($X \rightarrow 2\pi \frac{r_c}{l_s}$):

$$\begin{aligned}
X &\rightarrow 2\pi \frac{r_c}{l_s} \\
S_{E0, tot, compact} &= \\
&-T_{E0} [2\pi \frac{r_c}{l_s}]^{2N-4} \int dt Tr(\sum_{n_1, n_2=0}^9 (\langle [X^{n_1}, X^{n_2}] | [X^{n_1}, X^{n_2}] \rangle + \langle \{X^{n_1}, X^{n_2}\} | \{X^{n_1}, X^{n_2}\} \rangle)) \\
S_{E0, tot} &\Rightarrow -T_{E0} [2\pi \frac{r_c}{l_s}]^{2N-4} S_{D0, tot}
\end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

FIG. 4: By each compacting of a brane around a circle, a dimension could be lost

Above result shows that string theory could be a subgroup of a larger theory for example E-theory which its algebra could be compacted and reduced to known models. In fact, with each compacting, N -dimensional space could lose one dimension and reduce to $N-1$ dimensional space (See figure 4). Also, in this theory, all branes are built from

FIG. 5: Bases of a DNA could evolve, their topology changes and shrink to one point.

FIG. 6: A DNA could evolve, its topology changes and shrink to one point.

FIG. 7: By each half compacting of a brane around a circle, a scalar string decay into two fermions and one fermion from this pair could be lost.

FIG. 8: A DNA is coiled and some fermions obtain an extra freedom.

E0-branes. On the other hand, these branes could shrink to pint and their energies become one. Thus, total energy of a universe is a constant (See figure 3). This model could be applied for DNAs so. First, bases of a DNA could evolve, their topology changes and they shrink to a point (See figure 5). Also, total topology of a DNA could also evolve, its windings become open and shrink to a poin (See figure 6). If compactifications aren't complete, some scalars decay to fermionic fields. Also, half of fermions from emerged pairs could be lost (See figure 7). Again maybe occurs for a DNA. When a DNA coils around a circle, some of couplings between fermions become weaker and they obtain a new freedom (See figure 8).In these conditions, action includes fermions so:

$$\begin{aligned}
X &\longrightarrow \psi^\dagger \psi^\downarrow \\
\psi &\longrightarrow [2\pi \frac{r_c}{l_s}]^{1/2} \\
S_{E0,tot,halfcompacting} &= \\
&-T_{E0} [2\pi \frac{r_c}{l_s}]^{m/2} \int dt Tr (\sum_{n_1 \dots n_n=0}^{4N-2} (\langle [X^{n_1}, \dots, X^{n_{N-M}}, \psi^{m_1 \downarrow}, \dots, \psi^{m_{N-M} \downarrow}] [X^{n_1}, \dots, X^{n_{N-M}}, \psi^{m_1 \uparrow}, \dots, \psi^{m_{N-M} \uparrow}] \rangle + \\
&\langle \{X^{n_1}, \dots, X^{n_{N-M}}, \psi^{m_1 \downarrow}, \dots, \psi^{m_{N-M} \downarrow}\} \{X^{n_1}, \dots, X^{n_{N-M}}, \psi^{m_1 \uparrow}, \dots, \psi^{m_{N-M} \uparrow}\} \rangle)) \quad (26)
\end{aligned}$$

Any action includes scalars, fermions and gauge fields. Some strings are connected to branes by each two sides and produce gauge fields. While, some other strings are connected to branes only by an end and produce scalars. Also, some strings decay into pair of fermions. Half of these fermions may be lost by a compacting around a circle. We can write below laws:

$$\begin{aligned}
[X_\rho, X^i] &\longrightarrow \partial_\rho X^i \\
[X^a, X^b] &\longrightarrow A^{ab} \longrightarrow F^{ab} \longrightarrow \partial^a A^b - \partial^b A^a \\
\{X^a, X^b\} &\longrightarrow g^{ab} \longrightarrow \partial^a g^b + \partial^b g^a \\
[X^a, X^b, X^c] &\longrightarrow A^{abc} \longrightarrow F^{abc} \longrightarrow \partial^a A^{bc} + \partial^b A^{ac} - \partial^c A^{ba} \\
\{X^a, X^b, X^c\} &\longrightarrow g^{abc} \longrightarrow \partial^a g^{bc} + \partial^b g^{ac} + \partial^c g^{ab} \\
[X^a, \{X^b, X^c\}] &\longrightarrow \Gamma^{abc} \longrightarrow \partial^a g^{bc} - \partial^b g^{ca} + \partial^c g^{ab}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \{X^a, [X^b, X^c]\} &\longrightarrow Q^{abc} \longrightarrow \partial^a A^{bc} + \partial^b A^{ac} + \partial^c A^{ab} \\ \Sigma_{m=0}^9 &\rightarrow \Sigma_{a,b=0}^p \Sigma_{j=p+1}^9 \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

FIG. 9: N-dimensional symmetric and anti-symmetric fields.

Some of above gauge fields are completely symmetric and some are completely non-symmetric. Some of them are known and some aren't discovered. For example, complete symmetric field ($g_{abcd..}$) hasn't discovered yet. Reverse to graviton which is a closed string transverse to the brane, g is a completely confined field along the brane (See figure 9). A combinations of connected and non-connected strings follow of below rules:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle [X^a, X^i, X^j], [X^a, X^i, X^j] \rangle &= \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^{abc} \varepsilon^{abd} (\partial_c X_\alpha^i) (\partial_d X_\beta^i) \langle (T^\alpha, T^\beta) \rangle \sum_j [X^{j\alpha} T_\alpha, X^{j\beta} T_\beta] = \\ \frac{1}{2} \langle \partial^a X^i, \partial_a X^i \rangle &\sum_j [X^{j\alpha} T_\alpha, X^{j\beta} T_\beta] = \\ \frac{1}{2} \langle \partial^a X^i, \partial_a X^i \rangle &\sum_j F(X^j) \\ F(X) &= \sum_j [X^{j\alpha} T_\alpha, X^{j\beta} T_\beta] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \{X^a, X^i, X^j\}, \{X^a, X^i, X^j\} \rangle &= \frac{1}{2} \eta^{abc} \eta^{abd} (\partial_c X_\alpha^i) (\partial_d X_\beta^i) \langle (\bar{T}^\alpha, \bar{T}^\beta) \rangle \sum_j \sum_j \{X^{j\alpha} \bar{T}_\alpha, X^{j\beta} \bar{T}_\beta\} = \\ \frac{1}{2} \langle \bar{\partial}^a X^i, \bar{\partial}_a X^i \rangle &\sum_j \{X^{j\alpha} \bar{T}_\alpha, X^{j\beta} \bar{T}_\beta\} = \\ \frac{1}{2} \langle \bar{\partial}^a X^i, \bar{\partial}_a X^i \rangle &\sum_j G(X^j) \\ G(X) &= \sum_j \{X^{j\alpha} \bar{T}_\alpha, X^{j\beta} \bar{T}_\beta\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\langle [X^a, X^b, X^j], [X^a, X^b, X^j] \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^{abc} \varepsilon^{ade} (\partial_b \partial_c X_\alpha^i) (\partial_e \partial_d X_\beta^i) = \frac{1}{2} \langle \partial^b \partial^a X^i, \partial_b \partial_a X^i \rangle$$

$$\langle \{X^a, X^b, X^j\}, \{X^a, X^b, X^j\} \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \eta^{abc} \eta^{ade} (\partial_b \partial_c X_\alpha^i) (\partial_e \partial_d X_\beta^i) = \frac{1}{2} \langle \bar{\partial}^b \bar{\partial}^a X^i, \bar{\partial}_b \bar{\partial}_a X^i \rangle$$

$$\langle [X^a, X^b, X^c], [X^a, X^b, X^c] \rangle = -\lambda^2 \langle F^{abc}, F^{abc} \rangle$$

$$F_{abc} = \partial_a A_{bc} - \partial_b A_{ca} + \partial_c A_{ab}.$$

$$i, j = p + 1, \dots, 10 \quad a, b = 0, 1, \dots, p \quad m, n = 0, \dots, N$$

$$\langle \{X^a, X^b, X^c\}, \{X^a, X^b, X^c\} \rangle = -\lambda^2 \langle g^{abc}, g^{abc} \rangle$$

$$g_{abc} = \partial_a g_{bc} + \partial_b g_{ca} + \partial_c g_{ab}.$$

$$i, j = p + 1, \dots, N \quad a, b = 0, 1, \dots, p \quad m, n = 0, \dots, N$$

(28)

FIG. 10: In a DNA molecule, electrons are coupled by photons.

Above results show that how commutators connect gauge fields and scalars. Above results could be applied for a DNA so. Because, electrons are confined and exchange both types of photonic (See figure 10) and gravitational fields (See figure 11). Also, by each compacting, some fermions obtain a new type of freedom (See figure 12). Gauge fields and strings could decay to each other and fermions.

$$g_{ab}^U \rightarrow A_{ab'}^U A_{b'b}^U$$

$$g_{ab}^L \rightarrow A_{ab'}^L A_{b'b}^L$$

$$A_{ab}^U \rightarrow \psi_a^U \psi_b^U$$

$$A_{ab}^L \rightarrow \psi_a^L \psi_b^L$$

$$X \rightarrow \psi_a^U \psi_a^L + \psi_a^U A^{ab,L} \psi_b^U - \psi_a^L A^{ab,U} \psi_b^L + \Psi_a^U A^{ab,L} \Psi_b^U - \Psi_a^L A^{ab,U} \Psi_b^L + \Psi_a^U A^{ab,L} \psi_b^U - \psi_a^L A^{ab,U} \Psi_b^L +$$

FIG. 11: In a DNA molecule, electrons are coupled by gravitons.

FIG. 12: In a DNA molecule, electrons could be decoupled by compacting.

$$\Psi_a^U \Psi_a^L + A_a^U g^{ab,L} A_b^U + A_a^L g^{ab,U} A_b^L$$

$$\partial_a = \partial_a^U + \partial_a^L$$

$$\partial_a^U \psi_a^U = 1, \quad \partial_a^L \psi_a^L = 1. \quad (29)$$

Above relations and rules help us to obtain curvatures and gravitational waves from brackets:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\lambda}, \Gamma^\lambda_{\mu\nu} \rangle &= \langle [X^\rho, \{X_\sigma, X_\lambda\}], [X^\lambda, \{X_\mu, X_\nu\}] \rangle = \\ &= [X_\nu, [X^\rho, \{X_\sigma, X_\mu\}]] - [X_\mu, [X^\rho, \{X_\sigma, X_\nu\}]] + \\ &= [X^\rho, \{X_\lambda, X_\nu\}][X^\lambda, \{X_\sigma, X_\mu\}] - [X^\rho, \{X_\lambda, X_\mu\}][X^\lambda, \{X_\sigma, X_\nu\}] = \\ &= \partial_\nu \Gamma_{\sigma\mu}^\rho - \partial_\mu \Gamma_{\sigma\nu}^\rho + \Gamma_{\lambda\nu}^\rho \Gamma_{\sigma\mu}^\lambda - \Gamma_{\lambda\mu}^\rho \Gamma_{\sigma\nu}^\lambda = R_{\sigma\mu\nu}^\rho \\ \langle \Gamma_{abc}, \Gamma_{a'}^{bc} \rangle &= R_{aa'} \\ R_{MNP} &= R_{aa'} + R_{ia'} + R_{ij'} = R_{Free-Free} + R_{Free-Bound} + R_{Bound-Bound} \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

where $R_{Free-Free}$ is the gravitational tensor between two free fermions, $R_{Free-Bound}$ is the gravitational tensor between free and bound fermions and $R_{Bound-Bound}$ is the gravitational tensor between two bound fermions. Bound fermions are connected to brane, other fermion or atoms. Also, we can obtain the relation between four dimensional photons and fermions:

$$\begin{aligned} F_4 = F_{ab}^{ab} &= \langle F^{abc}, F_{abc} \rangle_{Free-Free} = \\ &= A^{ab} i \sigma_{ij}^2 \partial_a^i \psi_b^j + \sigma_{ij}^0 \psi^{\dagger a, i} \psi_a^j - \sigma_{ij}^1 \psi^{\dagger a, i} \psi_a^j + \\ &= \sigma_{i'i}^0 (\psi^{\dagger a, i'} i \sigma_{i'j}^0 \sigma_{jk}^1 \partial^{a, j} \psi_a^k) (\psi_a^{\dagger i} i \sigma_{ij}^0 \sigma_{jk}^1 \partial^{a, j} \psi_a^k) - \\ &= \sigma_{i'i}^1 (\psi^{\dagger a, i'} i \sigma_{i'j}^0 \sigma_{jk}^1 \partial^{a, j} \psi_a^k) (\psi_a^{\dagger i} i \sigma_{ij}^0 \sigma_{jk}^1 \partial^{a, j} \psi_a^k) - \\ &= \sigma_{i'i}^0 (\psi^{\dagger a, i'} i \sigma_{i'j}^1 \sigma_{jk}^1 \partial^{a, j} \psi_a^k) (\psi_a^{\dagger i} i \sigma_{ij}^1 \sigma_{jk}^1 \partial^{a, j} \psi_a^k) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_4 = F_{ab}^{ab} &= \langle F^{abc}, F_{abc} \rangle_{tot} = \\ &= \langle F^{abc}, F_{abc} \rangle_{Free-Free} + \langle F^{abc}, F_{abc} \rangle_{Free-Bound} + \langle F^{abc}, F_{abc} \rangle_{Bound-Bound} \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where $F_{Free-Free}$ is the photonic tensor between two free fermions, $F_{Free-Bound}$ is the photon tensor between free and bound fermions and $F_{Bound-Bound}$ is the photonic tensor between two bound fermions.

Now, using above results, we can calculate other communications in an E0-brane action:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \partial^b \partial^a X^i, \partial_b \partial_a X^i \rangle + \langle \bar{\partial}^b \bar{\partial}^a X^i, \bar{\partial}_b \bar{\partial}_a X^i \rangle + \langle \bar{\partial}^b \bar{\partial}^a X^i, \partial_b \partial_a X^i \rangle = \\ \Psi^{\dagger a, U} \langle F_{abc}, F^{a'bc} \rangle \Psi_{a'}^L + \Psi^{\dagger a, L} \langle F_{abc}, F^{a'bc} \rangle \Psi_{a'}^U - \Psi^{\dagger a, U} \langle F_{abc}, F^{a'bc} \rangle \Psi_{a'}^U \\ - \Psi^{\dagger a, L} \langle F_{abc}, F^{a'bc} \rangle \Psi_{a'}^L + \Psi^{\dagger a, L} \Psi^{\dagger d, U} \partial_d \partial^{d'} \langle F_{abc}, F^{a'bc} \rangle \Psi_{a'}^L \Psi_{d'}^U \\ - \Psi^{\dagger a, L} \Psi^{\dagger d, U} \partial_d \langle F_{abc}, F^{a'bc} \rangle \Psi_{a'}^L - \Psi^{\dagger a, U} \Psi^{\dagger d, L} \partial_d \langle F_{abc}, F^{a'bc} \rangle \Psi_{a'}^U \\ + \psi^{\dagger i, U} \langle F_{ijk}, F^{i'jk} \rangle \psi_{i'}^L + \psi^{\dagger i, L} \langle F_{ijk}, F^{i'jk} \rangle \psi_{i'}^U - \psi^{\dagger i, U} \langle F_{ijk}, F^{i'jk} \rangle \psi_{i'}^U \\ - \psi^{\dagger i, L} \langle F_{ijk}, F^{i'jk} \rangle \psi_{i'}^L + \psi^{\dagger i, L} \psi^{\dagger m, U} \partial_m \partial^{m'} \langle F_{ijk}, F^{i'jk} \rangle \psi_{i'}^L \psi_{m'}^U \\ - \psi^{\dagger i, L} \psi^{\dagger m, U} \partial_m \langle F_{ijk}, F^{i'jk} \rangle \psi_{i'}^L - \psi^{\dagger i, U} \psi^{\dagger m, L} \partial_m \langle F_{ijk}, F^{i'jk} \rangle \psi_{i'}^U \\ + \Psi^{\dagger a, U} \langle F_{abc}, F^{i'bc} \rangle \psi_{i'}^L + \Psi^{\dagger a, L} \langle F_{abc}, F^{i'bc} \rangle \psi_{i'}^U - \Psi^{\dagger a, U} \langle F_{abc}, F^{i'bc} \rangle \psi_{i'}^U \\ - \Psi^{\dagger a, L} \langle F_{abc}, F^{i'bc} \rangle \psi_{i'}^L + \Psi^{\dagger a, L} \Psi^{\dagger d, U} \partial_d \partial^{d'} \langle F_{abc}, F^{j'bc} \rangle \psi_{j'}^L \psi_{d'}^U \\ - \Psi^{\dagger a, L} \Psi^{\dagger d, U} \partial_d \langle F_{abc}, F^{i'bc} \rangle \psi_{i'}^L - \Psi^{\dagger a, U} \Psi^{\dagger d, L} \partial_d \langle F_{abc}, F^{i'bc} \rangle \psi_{i'}^U + \\ \Psi^{\dagger a, U} R_{aa'}^{anti-parallel} \Psi_{aa'}^{a', L} + \Psi^{\dagger a, L} R_{aa'}^{anti-parallel} \Psi_{aa'}^{a', U} \\ - \Psi^{\dagger a, U} R_{aa'}^{parallel} \Psi_{aa'}^{a', U} - \Psi^{\dagger a, L} R_{aa'}^{parallel} \Psi_{aa'}^{a', L} \\ + \Psi^{\dagger a, L} \Psi^{\dagger d, U} \partial_d \partial^{d'} (R_{aa'}^{parallel} + R_{aa'}^{anti-parallel}) \Psi_{aa'}^{a', L} \Psi_{d'}^U \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\Psi^{\dagger a,L} \Psi^{\dagger d,U} \partial_d (R_{aa'}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{aa'}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \Psi^{a',L} \\
& -\Psi^{\dagger a,U} \Psi^{\dagger d,L} \partial_d (R_{aa'}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{aa'}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \Psi^{a',U} \\
& + \psi^{\dagger i,U} R_{ii'}^{\text{anti-parallel}} \psi^{i',L} + \psi^{\dagger i,L} R_{ii'}^{\text{anti-parallel}} \psi^{i',U} \\
& - \psi^{\dagger i,U} R_{ii'}^{\text{parallel}} \psi^{i',U} - \psi^{\dagger i,L} R_{ii'}^{\text{parallel}} \psi^{i',L} \\
& + \psi^{\dagger i,L} \psi^{\dagger m,U} \partial_m \partial^{m'} (R_{ij'}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{ij'}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \psi^{i',L} \psi_{m'}^U \\
& - \psi^{\dagger i,L} \psi^{\dagger m,U} \partial_m (R_{ij'}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{ij'}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \psi^{i',L} \\
& - \psi^{\dagger i,U} \psi^{\dagger m,L} \partial_m (R_{ij'}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{ij'}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \psi^{i',U} \\
& + \Psi^{\dagger a,U} R_{ai'}^{\text{anti-parallel}} \psi^{i',L} + \Psi^{\dagger a,L} R_{ai'}^{\text{anti-parallel}} \psi^{i',U} \\
& - \Psi^{\dagger a,U} R_{ai'}^{\text{parallel}} \psi^{i',U} - \Psi^{\dagger a,L} R_{ai'}^{\text{parallel}} \psi^{i',L} \\
& + \Psi^{\dagger a,L} \Psi^{\dagger d,U} \partial_d \partial^{i'} (R_{ai'}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{ai'}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \psi_{j'}^L \psi^{i',U} \\
& - \Psi^{\dagger a,L} \Psi^{\dagger d,U} \partial_d (R_{ai'}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{ai'}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \psi^{i',L} \\
& - \Psi^{\dagger a,U} \Psi^{\dagger d,L} \partial_d (R_{ai'}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{ai'}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \psi^{i',U} + \dots
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \approx (R_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{parallel}})^2 + (R_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{anti-parallel}})^2 + (R_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}})^2 \\
& + (R_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}})^2 + (R_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}})^2 + (R_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}})^2 \\
& + (R_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{parallel}} R_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \partial^2 (R_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \\
& + (R_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} R_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \partial^2 (R_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \\
& + (R_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} R_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \partial^2 (R_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) + \\
& (([F^4]_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{parallel}})^2 + ([F^4]_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{anti-parallel}})^2 + ([F^4]_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}})^2 \\
& + ([F^4]_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}})^2 + ([F^4]_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}})^2 + ([F^4]_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}})^2 \\
& + ([F^4]_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{parallel}} [F^4]_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \partial^2 ([F^4]_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{parallel}} + [F^4]_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \\
& + [F^4]_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} [F^4]_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}} \partial^2 ([F^4]_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} + [F^4]_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \\
& + ([F^4]_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} [F^4]_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \partial^2 ([F^4]_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) + \\
& (([F^4]_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{parallel}} R_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{parallel}}) + ([F^4]_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{anti-parallel}} R_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) + ([F^4]_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} R_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}}) \\
& + ([F^4]_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}} R_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) + ([F^4]_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} R_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}}) + ([F^4]_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}} R_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \\
& + ([F^4]_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{parallel}} [F^4]_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \partial^2 (R_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{\text{Free-Free}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \\
& + [F^4]_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} [F^4]_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}} \partial^2 (R_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{\text{Free-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \\
& + ([F^4]_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} [F^4]_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}) \partial^2 (R_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{parallel}} + R_{\text{Bound-Bound}}^{\text{anti-parallel}}), \tag{32}
\end{aligned}$$

Also, other symmetric and anti-symmetric gauge fields have the below relations with each other and brackets:

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle g^\rho{}_{\sigma\lambda}, g^\lambda{}_{\mu\nu} \rangle &= P_{\sigma\mu\nu}^\rho \\
P_4 &= P_{\text{Free-Free}} + P_{\text{Free-Bound}} + P_{\text{Bound-Bound}} \tag{33}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle Q^\rho{}_{\sigma\lambda}, Q^\lambda{}_{\mu\nu} \rangle &= Q_{\sigma\mu\nu}^\rho \\
Q_4 &= Q_{\text{Free-Free}} + Q_{\text{Free-Bound}} + Q_{\text{Bound-Bound}} \tag{34}
\end{aligned}$$

Now, we can use of above relations between brackets and gauge fields to obtain the exact form of Mp-branes and more generally Ep-branes. These branes are built by summing over M0-branes and E0-branes (See figure 13). Thus, their energies are equal to sum over energies of M0-branes and E0-branes. For generalized Mp-branes, we have:

$$E_{Mp,tot} = \sum_{n_1 \dots n_n=0}^p E_{M0,tot} = \frac{p(p+1)}{2}$$

FIG. 13: Ep-branes are formed by joining E0-branes

$$\begin{aligned}
1 &= E'_{Mp,tot} = E_{Mp,tot} \frac{2}{p(p+1)} \\
&\sum_{n_1 \dots n_n=0}^p \sum_{n_1 \dots n_n=0}^9 \rightarrow \int d^{p+1} \sum_{n_1 \dots n_n=p+1}^{10} \\
1 &= E'_{Mp,tot} = -S'_{Mp,tot} = \\
&+T'_{Mp} \int d^{p+1} Tr(\sum_{n_1 \dots n_n=p+1}^{10} (\langle [X^{n_1}, \dots, X^{n_3}] | [X^{n_1}, \dots, X^{n_3}] \rangle + \\
&\langle \{X^{n_1}, \dots, X^{n_3}\} | \{X^{n_1}, \dots, X^{n_3}\} \rangle + \\
&\langle \{X^{n_1}, \dots, [\dots, X^{n_3}] \} | \{X^{n_1}, \dots, \{ \dots, X^{n_3} \} \} \rangle + \dots)
\end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

Or more generally, for Ep-branes with 4N-2-dimensional space-times, we can write

$$\begin{aligned}
1 &= E'_{Ep,tot} = \sum_{n_1 \dots n_n=0}^p E_{E0,tot} = \\
&+T'_{Ep} \int d^{p+1} Tr(\sum_{n_1 \dots n_n=p+1}^{4N-2} (\langle [X^{n_1}, \dots, \psi_{n_m}, [\dots], \{\dots\}, X^{n_N}] | [X^{n_1}, \dots, \psi_{n_m}, [\dots], \{\dots\}, X^{n_N}] \rangle + \\
&\langle \{X^{n_1}, \dots, [\dots], \dots, \psi_{n_m}, \{\dots\}, \dots, X^{n_N}\} | \{X^{n_1}, \dots, [\dots], \dots, \psi_{n_m}, \{\dots\}, \dots, X^{n_N}\} \rangle \\
&+ \dots)
\end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

Above action includes both symmetrical and anti-symmetrical brackets. Each bracket corresponds to a gauge field. Thus, above action produces various types of gauge fields with different spins. We can use of this action for a 4n-2 dimensional space-time system with N-dimensional algebra. This system could be a DNA or a graphene.

III. CURRENT DENSITY AND SUPERCONDUCTIVITY THROUGH MODIFIED ALGEBRA IN A DNA

In this section, we will calculate total current density of a DNA by regarding all interactions between atoms and show that this current is zero and topology of a DNA shrinks to point. However, each part of a DNA acts like a circuit and produce a separate current. Summing over these currents give zero (See figure 14). To this aim, we generalize string theory and M-theory to ten dimensions and design an special algebra and model for a DNA.

Up to now, we have re-considered string theory and M-theory and relations between brackets, scalars and gauge fields. Now, we like to use of these concepts in considering topology and evolutions of a DNA. First, using above energy, we can calculate the energy between three atoms in a vertex of hexagonal/pentagonal molecule:

$$\begin{aligned}
1 &= E_{THREE-ATOM,tot} = \\
&+T'_{THREE} \int d^{p+1} Tr(\sum_{n_1 \dots n_n=p+1}^N ([R_4]^2 + [F_4]^2 + [P_4]^2 + [Q_4]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

FIG. 14: Summing over currents of a DNA become zero

$$[R_4][F_4] + [P_4][Q_4] + [R_4][Q_4] + [R_4][P_4] + [F_4][Q_4] + [R_4]^2 \partial^2 [R_4] + [F_4]^2 \partial^2 [F_4] + [P_4]^2 \partial^2 [P_4] + [Q_4]^2 \partial^2 [Q_4] + \dots \Big|_{\substack{\text{parallel/anti-parallel-parallel/anti-parallel-parallel} \\ \text{Free/Bound-Free/Bound}}} \quad (37)$$

where we have used of below rules, and replace brackets with gauge fields:

$$\langle [X^{n_1}, \{X^{n_2}, X^{n_3}, [X^{n_4}, X^{n_5}]\}] | [X^{n_1}, \{X^{n_2}, X^{n_3}, [X^{n_4}, X^{n_5}]\}] \rangle \rightarrow T_5 \quad (38)$$

$$\langle [X^{n_1}, X^{n_2}, X^{n_3}, X^{n_4}, X^{n_5}] | [X^{n_1}, X^{n_2}, X^{n_3}, X^{n_4}, X^{n_5}] \rangle \rightarrow F_5 \quad (39)$$

$$\langle \{X^{n_1}, X^{n_2}, X^{n_3}, X^{n_4}, X^{n_5}\} | \{X^{n_1}, X^{n_2}, X^{n_3}, X^{n_4}, X^{n_5}\} \rangle \rightarrow P_5 \quad (40)$$

$$\langle [X^{n_1}, X^{n_2}, X^{n_3}, \{X^{n_4}, X^{n_5}\}] | [X^{n_1}, X^{n_2}, X^{n_3}, \{X^{n_4}, X^{n_5}\}] \rangle \rightarrow R_5 \quad (41)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle g^{\rho\alpha}_{\sigma\lambda}, g^{\lambda}_{\mu\nu\beta} \rangle &= P^{\rho\alpha}_{\sigma\mu\nu\beta} \\ P_5 &= P_{Free-Free} + P_{Free-Bound} + P_{Bound-Bound} \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle Q^{\rho\alpha}_{\sigma\lambda\beta}, Q^{\lambda\alpha}_{\mu\nu\beta} \rangle &= Q^{\rho\alpha}_{\sigma\mu\nu\beta} \\ Q_5 &= Q_{Free-Free} + Q_{Free-Bound} + Q_{Bound-Bound} \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

Above energy depends on the gauge fields, gravitons and other exchanged waves between three atoms (See figure 15). Each atom of a hexagonal/pentagonal base can interact with one, two or more atoms of other base (See figure 16). Using previous results, we can write:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= E_{twomolecules,tot} = \\ &+ T'_{molecule} \int d^{p+1} Tr(\Sigma_{n_1 \dots n_n = p+1}^N (\Sigma_{i,j,k=1}^{i=6,j=M,k=5} vertex_{ij}^{three-atom} vertex_{ij}^{twomolecules} vertex_{jk}^{three-atom})) \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

where

FIG. 15: A vertex of three atoms and its gauge fields in a DNA

FIG. 16: Two vertexes and their gauge fields in a DNA

$$\begin{aligned}
 vertex_{ij}^{three-atom} = & ([R_4]^2 + [F_4]^2 + [P_4]^2 + [Q_4]^2 + \\
 & [R_4][F_4] + [P_4][Q_4] + [R_4][Q_4] + [R_4][P_4] + [F_4][Q_4] + \\
 & [R_4]^2 \partial^2 [R_4] + [F_4]^2 \partial^2 [F_4] + [P_4]^2 \partial^2 [P_4] + [Q_4]^2 \partial^2 [Q_4] + \dots) \Big|_{Free/Bound-Free/Bound}^{parallel/anti-parallel-parallel/anti-parallel-parallel} (45)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 vertex_{ij}^{twomolecules} = & ([R_5]^2 + [F_5]^2 + [P_5]^2 + [Q_5]^2 + [T_5]^2 + \\
 & [R_5][F_5] + [R_5][T_5] + [P_5][Q_5] + [R_5][Q_5] + [R_5][P_5] + [F_5][Q_5] + \\
 & [R_5]^2 \partial^2 [R_5] + [F_5]^2 \partial^2 [F_5] + [P_5]^2 \partial^2 [P_5] + [T_5]^2 \partial^2 [T_5] + \dots) \Big|_{Free/Bound-Free/Bound}^{parallel/anti-parallel-parallel/anti-parallel-parallel} (46)
 \end{aligned}$$

Above results show that how we could obtain energy of exchanged waves in terms of vertexes in a DNA. To calculate total energy of a DNA, we need to use of generalized E-model. Because, there are many compactings and interactions and M-theory couldnt respond. We can write:

Above results show that total energy of a DNA could be equal to a constant. This means that topology of a DNA could shrink to a point (See figure 14). Using above energy, we can obtain total current:

$$\begin{aligned}
0 = I_{DNA} &= \frac{dE_{DNA,tot}}{dt} = \\
&+ T'_{DNA} \int d^{p+1} Tr(\Sigma_{n_1 \dots n_n = p+1}^N \times \\
&(\Sigma_{i,j,k,l,m,n=1}^{i=6,j,l,m,n=M,k=5} [\overline{vertex}_{ij}^{three-atom} \overline{vertex}_{ijl}^{twomolecules} \overline{vertex}_{jk}^{three-atom} \overline{vertex}_{lm}^{compact1} \overline{vertex}_{mn}^{compact2} \dots] + \\
&[\overline{vertex}_{ij}^{three-atom} \overline{vertex}_{ijl}^{twomolecules} \overline{vertex}_{jk}^{three-atom} \overline{vertex}_{lm}^{compact1} \overline{vertex}_{mn}^{compact2} \dots] + \\
&[\overline{vertex}_{ij}^{three-atom} \overline{vertex}_{ijl}^{twomolecules} \overline{vertex}_{jk}^{three-atom} \overline{vertex}_{lm}^{compact1} \overline{vertex}_{mn}^{compact2} \dots] + \dots) \quad (52)
\end{aligned}$$

where we have used of below rules:

$$\begin{aligned}
\overline{vertex} &= \frac{dvertex}{dt} = \frac{dvertex}{dl} \frac{dl}{dt} \\
\frac{dl}{dt} &\rightarrow [X^0, , [\dots], \{\dots\}, , X^{n_N}] \\
&\rightarrow \sqrt{[X^{n_1}, , [\dots], \{\dots\}, , X^{n_N}] | [X^{n_1}, [\dots], \{\dots\}, , X^{n_N}] \rightarrow \sqrt{U_N, T_N, R_N, O_N, P_N, Q_N, F_N} \quad (53)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\overline{vertex}_{ij}^{compactN} &= ([R_{N+5}]^{2+1/2} + [F_{N+5}]^{2+1/2} + [P_{N+5}]^{2+1/2} + [Q_{N+5}]^{2+1/2} + \\
&[R_{N+5}][F_{N+5}]^{3/2} + [P_{N+5}]^{3/2}[Q_{N+5}] + [R_{N+5}]^{3/2}[Q_{N+5}] + [R_{N+5}]^{3/2}[P_{N+5}] + [F_{N+5}][Q_{N+5}]^{3/2} + \\
&[R_{N+5}]^{2+1/2}\partial^2[R_{N+5}] + [F_{N+5}]^{2+1/2}\partial^2[F_{N+5}] + [P_{N+5}]^{2+1/2}\partial^2[P_{N+5}] + [Q_{N+5}]^{2+1/2}\partial^2[Q_{N+5}] + \dots \\
&[O_{N+5}]^{2+1/2} + [T_{N+5}]^{2+1/2} + [U_{N+5}]^{2+1/2} + [Y_{N+5}]^{2+1/2} + \\
&[O_{N+5}][R_{N+5}] + [U_{N+5}][Y_{N+5}]^{3/2} + [U_{N+5}][Q_{N+5}]^{3/2} + [R_{N+5}][Y_{N+5}]^{3/2} + [O_{N+5}]^{3/2}[Q_{N+5}] + \\
&[U_{N+5}]^{2+1/2}\partial^{2+1/2}[U_{N+5}] + [O_{N+5}]^{2+1/2}\partial^2[O_{N+5}] + [Y_{N+5}]^{2+1/2}\partial^2[Y_{N+5}] + [T_{N+5}]^{2+1/2}\partial^2[T_{N+5}] + \\
&\dots)_{\substack{\text{parallel/anti-parallel-parallel/anti-parallel-parallel} \\ \text{Free/Bound-Free/Bound}}} ij \quad (54)
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, a DNA has a constant energy and its total current is zero. However, each part of a DNA has its self current.

$$\begin{aligned}
0 = \mathbf{I}_{DNA} &= \Sigma_{i,j,k,l,m,n=1}^{i=6,j,l,m,n=M,k=5} \mathbf{J}_{ijklmn} \\
\implies 0 = \mathbf{B}_{DNA} &= \Sigma_{i,j,k,l,m,n=1}^{i=6,j,l,m,n=M,k=5} \mathbf{B}_{ijklmn} \quad (55)
\end{aligned}$$

where B could be magnetic field or each other type of fields. Each hexagonal/pentagonal molecule in a DNA has itself current. Also, each compacting of bases in a DNA induces a new current. However, summing over all currents is zero. This means that each base has itself radiation. Even each gene has its self radiation and acts like the receiver or sender of waves. However, in normal conditions, these waves cancel the effect of each other and total wave and current of a DNA is zero.

Assume that an external current enter from one side to a DNA. This current changes the current density in a local point of a DNA. To save stability of a DNA, we need that total current be zero:

$$\begin{aligned}
0 = \mathbf{I}_{DNA} &= J_{external} + \Sigma_{i,j,k,l,m,n=1}^{i=6,j,l,m,n=M,k=5} [\mathbf{J}_{ijklmn} + \mathbf{J}'_{111111}] = \\
&\Sigma_{i,j,k,l,m,n=1}^{i=6,j,l,m,n=M,k=5} [\mathbf{J}_{ijklmn} + \mathbf{J}'_{111111} + \mathbf{J}'_{6MMMM5}] \quad (56)
\end{aligned}$$

where:

$$\mathbf{J}'_{111111} = -\mathbf{J}'_{6MMMM5} = J_{external} \quad (57)$$

FIG. 18: A DNA could be like a superconductor which doesn't let to magnetic fields for entering to it.

Above results show that each external current could enter from one side into a DNA within the nucleus and out from other side immediately and without any resistance. This could be signature of superconductivity (See figure 18). Because, total magnetic wave within a DNA is zero and all currents could be transformed immediately.

Now, assume that a DNA divide completely into two parts and each part creates itself cell. We can write:

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 &= \mathbf{I}_{initialDNA} = \left[\sum_{i,j,k,l,m,n=1}^{i=6,j,l,m,n=M/2,k=5} \mathbf{J}_{ijklmn} + \sum_{i',j',k',l',m',n'=1}^{i'=6,j',l',m',n'=M/2,k'=5} \mathbf{J}'_{i'j'k'l'm'n'} \right] \\
 \implies 0 &= \mathbf{B}_{DNA} = \left[\sum_{i,j,k,l,m,n=1}^{i=6,j,l,m,n=M/2,k=5} \mathbf{B}_{ijklmn} + \sum_{i',j',k',l',m',n'=1}^{i'=6,j',l',m',n'=M/2,k'=5} \mathbf{B}'_{i'j'k'l'm'n'} \right] \quad (58)
 \end{aligned}$$

FIG. 19: If an initial DNA divides into two daughter DNAs, they be confirmed to each other and their total currents become zero.

Above equation shows that two daughter DNAs are completely confined. Each change in a current density or waves in a part of a DNA could be transmitted immediately to other DNA and total current of system becomes zero (See figure 19). This means that if, all human's cells are originated from a cell, they could communicate with each other immediately. For example, if a cell becomes infectious or a DNA experiences extra waves of a virus, all other cells become aware without any delay in time.

In real world, we couldnt observe interactions and exchanged waves between DNAs. It seems that confined DNAs exchange non-observable fields. In previous section, we have introduced a new ful symmetric field ("g"). This field couldnt be observed in our universe. Maybe, our universe is located on the connected region of two branes (See figure 20). Each field that live on brane 1,could be observed however, fields on brane 2 couldn't be observed. Only, we

could find their signatures. For example, we know that according to Pauli principle, by changing spin of an electron, the spin of other electron in a pair could be changed immediately. This could be a result of confinement of electrons through this full symmetric field which live on brane 2. For confined DNAs, we can write:

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &= \mathbf{I}_{initialDNA} = [\sum_{i,j,k,l,m,n=1}^{i=6,j,l,m,n=M/2,k=5} \mathbf{J}_{ijklmn} + \sum_{i',j',k',l',m',n'=1}^{i'=6,j',l',m',n'=M/2,k'=5} \mathbf{J}_{i'j'k'l'm'n'}] \\
\implies 0 &= \mathbf{g}_{DNA} = [\sum_{i,j,k,l,m,n=1}^{i=6,j,l,m,n=M/2,k=5} \mathbf{g}_{ijklmn} + \sum_{i',j',k',l',m',n'=1}^{i'=6,j',l',m',n'=M/2,k'=5} \mathbf{g}_{i'j'k'l'm'n'}]
\end{aligned} \tag{59}$$

Above equation shows that for a parent DNA, total current and wave is zero. However, by transforming a DNA into two daughter ones, each new DNA could have its current and waves. However, total current and waves of two DNAs are zero. This means that two DNAs are confined through some fields which aren't observed in our universe. For example, assume that we live on connected regions of two branes. In these conditions, some full symmetric waves which live in brane 2 may be non-observable however connect two confined DNAs (See figure 20).

FIG. 20: DNAs are connected by full-symmetric waves in non-observable brane

IV. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this research, we have proposed a new model to consider superconductivity of DNAs and calculate their currents and radiated waves. In this model, our DNAs were born on the connected regions of two interacting branes. These branes are formed from zero-dimensional branes and shrink topologically to a point. Each brane has $4N-2$ dimensional space-time with N -dimensional algebra. By compacting branes, some fermions were emerged which some of them were lost and some others became free. Also, each brane has itself symmetric and non-symmetric fields. In connected region, only gauge fields of one brane could be observed, however, the signature of second brane could be detected. For example, two DNAs could be connected through some full symmetric waves of brane 2 and some currents may be exchanged between them. However, in connected region, they are separated completely and their total currents are zero. Also, they show the superconductivity behaviour and don't accept any external field.

Acknowledgments

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